

Halogenation of 2-Methylbenzimidazole

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The halogenation of 2-methylbenzimidazole and bromination of 2-nitroaniline are described.

The direct halogenation of benzimidazole has received little attention. Bromination¹ of 2-methylbenzimidazole in acetic acid and chlorination² of 2,5(6)-dimethylbenzimidazole with bleaching powder afforded mono-, di, and tri- halobenzimidazoles. Introduction of the halogen in benzene nucleus has been suggested through formation of an unstable halo-aminobenzimidazole which on refluxing with benzene or aniline provides halobenzimidazole. Chlorination of 2-aminobenzimidazole with hydrochloric acid and hydrogen peroxide afforded 5(6)-chloro derivative³. 5(6)-Aminobenzimidazole⁴, on chlorination and bromination, produced 4(7)-chloro- and 4,6(7,5)-dibromobenzimidazole, respectively.

A cleavage of benzimidazoles led to the fission of the heterocyclic five-membered ring⁵ to yield *NN'*-diacetyl-*o*-phenylenediamine when it was allowed to react with carboxylic acid anhydrides⁶⁻⁷ and acid chlorides⁸⁻¹⁰, whereas with alkyl iodide¹¹ *NN'*-dialkyl-*o*-phenylenediamines were obtained.

Bromination of 2-methylbenzimidazole furnished 2-methyl-5(6)-bromobenzimidazole (m.p. 215-16°), corresponding with the compound prepared by Phillips¹² from 4-bromo-*o*-phenylenediamine and acetic acid, but differing from the product claimed by Baczynski and Niementowski¹. 2-Methyl-4(7)-bromobenzimidazole¹³ (m.p. 168°) was synthesised from 3-bromo-1, 2-diaminobenzene and acetic acid, which differed in physical properties of the product obtained by Baczynski *et al.*¹.

Bromination of 2-methyl-5(6)-bromobenzimidazole provided 2-methyl-4,6 (5,7)-dibromobenzimidazole which did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample^{13a}, but differed from Baczynski's product¹.

1. Baczynski, and Niementowski, *Bull. Acad. Sci. Cracow*, 1902, 421; *Chem. Zentr.*, 1902 II, 940. Niementowski, *Ber.*, 1898, **31**, 314; 1892, **25**, 864.
2. Bamberger and Lorenzen, *Annalen*, 1893, **273**, 269.
3. Leonard *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, **69**, 2459.
4. Fries *et al.*, *Annalen*, 1927, **454**, 121.
5. Salweicz and Jasinski, *Roczniki Chem.*, 1961, **35**, 165.
6. (a) Bistrzycki and Przeworski, *Ber.*, 1912, **45**, 3483.
(b) Heller, *Ber.*, 1904, **37**, 3112.
7. Oddo and Raffa, *Gazzetta*, 1938, **68**, 199; 1937, **67**, 537.
8. Briuk and Folkers, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 2951.
9. Gerngross, *Ber.*, 1913, **46**, 1913.
10. Witt, *Ber.*, 1874, **7**, 1604.
11. Bamberger and Berle, *Annalen*, 1893, **273**, 342.
12. Phillips, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1143.
13. (a) Dandegaonker and Revanker, *J. Karnatak. Univ.*, 1961, **6**, 25; (b) Dandegaonker, and Shastri, *Monatsh.*, 1965, **95**, 614.

Chlorination of 2-methylbenzimidazole with either calcium hypochlorite or hydrochloric acid and hydrogen peroxide yielded only 2-methyl-4-chlorobenzimidazole which did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample, but differed from those reported by Fischer¹⁴ (m. p. 199°) and Van Lare¹⁵ (m.p. 215-18°). It did not undergo further chlorination. This supports the difference in the reactivity of chlorine and bromine.

Bromination of *o*-nitroaniline in acetic acid with two molecules of bromine has been reported to yield dibromo-*o*-nitroaniline¹⁶. It is evident from the present investigations that a mixture of 5-bromo-, 4-bromo-, and 4,6-dibromo-*o*-nitroanilines is formed, instead of only dibromo compound. These bromonitroanilines do not depress the m.p. of authentic compounds. The formation of 5-bromo-*o*-nitroaniline could be accounted due to production of 2-nitroaniline hydrobromide. The cleavage of imidazole ring of benzimidazole with acetic anhydride or benzoyl chloride probably results in *sym.*-diacyl- or-dibenzoyl-*o*-phenylenediamine derivative, but all attempts to hydrolyse them with acid or base to yield free *o*-phenylenediamine failed, due to recyclisation.

Methyl iodide in presence of an alkali cleaved the benzimidazole, producing the corresponding *NN'*-dimethyl-*o*-phenylenediamine.

The UV absorption of benzimidazoles (Table I) confirms the position occupied by halogen in halogenation of 2-methylbenzimidazole. These spectra are identical with those of authentic samples and confirm the findings¹⁷ and conclusion of Leandri and co-workers¹⁸ that introduction of a halogen causes bathochromic displacements with increased intensity of characteristic bands of the benzimidazole ring. 5(6)-Chloro isomer shows increased intensity and the displacement of main of band towards longer wave length compared with bands of 4-chloro- and 4,6-dichloro-benzimidazoles. The latter have intramolecular hydrogen bonding and absorb at shorter wave length with decreased intensity¹⁹. The 4-bromo-, 4, 6-dibromo-, and 5-bromo- 2-methylbenzimidazoles also show similar absorption

14. *Ber.*, 1905, **38**, 328.

15. Van Lare U. S. P. 2, 739149/1957; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, **51**, 903.

16. Jackson and Russe, *Amer. Chem. J.*, 1906, **35**, 150.

17. Steck *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3406.

18. *Gazzetta*, 1955, **85**, 769.

19. Burawoy *et al.*, *J. Chem Soc.*, 1952, 2310, 3734; 1955, 3727,

and intensity differences. Rabiger and Joullie's²⁰ observations are very similar with those recorded herein.

The spectra of *NN'*-dimethyl-*o*-phenylenediamine (Table II) is similar to that recorded for *o*-phenylenediamine²¹⁻²². The chloro- and bromo-*o*-phenylenediamines show a bathochromic shift.

TABLE I

No.	Benzimidazoles.	$\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ).					
1	5-Chloro-2-methyl-	249 (4.690)	255 (4.730)	sh 281 (4.350)		295 (3.687)	
2	4-Chloro-2-methyl-	248 (3.737)	253 (3.856)	259 (3.887) 265 (3.838)	286 (4.491)		
3	4,6-Dichloro-2-methyl-	250 (3.840)	257 (3.853)		287 (3.572)		
4	5-Bromo-2-methyl-	sh 250 (3.756)	255 (3.828)	259 (3.794)	288 (3.832)	295 (2.804)	
5	4,6-Dibromo-2-methyl-	252 (3.803)		259 (3.723)	288 (2.726)	294 (2.733)	

N. B. Log ϵ values are shown in parenthesis.

Sh denotes shoulder.

TABLE II

No.	<i>o</i> -Phenylene- diamines.	$\lambda_{\max}$ (m μ).					
1	<i>o</i> -Phenylene- diamine ²¹	207 (4.6)	230.0 (3.83)		280 (3.21)	289.0 (3.47)	
	Du ²²		236.6 (3.88)			292.7 (3.58)	
2	<i>NN'</i> -Dimethyl-		225.0 (3.79)	258 (3.75)	281 (3.65)		
3	<i>NN'</i> -Dimethyl- 5-chloro-		224.0 (4.12)	265 (3.66)		296.0 (3.51)	305 (3.47)
4	<i>NN'</i> -Dimethyl- 5-bromo-, HCl		224.0 (4.13)	266 (3.86)		294.0 (3.95)	304 (3.04)
5	<i>NN'</i> -Dimethyl- 3,5-dibromo-, HCl		244.0 (4.44)	250 (3.90)			316 (3.40)

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromination of o-Nitroaniline.—Bromine (120 g., 0.66*M*) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) was added dropwise over an hour to a well-stirred solution of *o*-nitroaniline (46.0 g., 0.33*M*),

20. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 915; *J. Org. Chem.*, 1964, 29, 470.

21. Gallagher, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, 67, 807.

22. Morton and Stubbs, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 1347.

dissolved in acetic acid (200 ml), and the mixture was left overnight. The precipitate (A) was filtered. The filtrate on dilution with cold water afforded 4,6-dibromo-2-nitroaniline (28.0 g., 29%), m.p. 126-27°.

The precipitate (A) was neutralised with sodium bicarbonate; the bromonitroanilines, m.p. 80-85° (42.0 g., 69%), thus obtained, on fractional crystallisation from 50% ethanol, afforded 4-bromo- and 5-bromo-2-nitroanilines.

TABLE A

2-Nitroarilines.	M. P.	Colour.	% Yield.
4-Bromo-	109-10°	Orange needles	59.5
5-Bromo-	96-97°	Yellow „	26.4
4,6-Dibromo-	126-27°	Lemon-yellow „	13.5

Reduction of Bromo-2-nitroaniline.—4,6-Dibromo-2-nitroaniline (20 g.), tin (40 g.) and HCl (conc., 100 ml) were mixed and heated on a water bath. More HCl (150 ml) was added over 2 hr. and heating continued till the colour had disappeared. The reaction product was filtered; the filtrate on neutralisation with KOH (10%) at 0° was extracted with ether. The ether extracts, dried over solid NaOH, afforded 4,6-dibromo-*o*-phenylenediamine¹⁶ (10 g., 55%), m.p. 81-82°.

4-Bromo-*o*-phenylenediamine²³ (pinkish, yield 56%, m.p. 61-62°) and 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine¹⁰ (45%, m.p. 76°) were obtained from the corresponding halo-*o*-nitroaniline by the above procedure.

4, 6-Dichloro-*o*-phenylenediamine⁶ (51%, m.p. 60°) was obtained from 4, 6-dichloro-*o*-nitroaniline by reduction at 80-90° with SnCl₂ and HCl.

Halogenation of 2-Methylbenzimidazole

(A). *Bromination with 1 Mole of Bromine.*—Bromine (12.59 g.) in acetic acid (75 ml) was added to a well-stirred solution of 2-methylbenzimidazole (10.0 g., 1 M) in acetic acid (75 ml) at 0° over 30 min. and the mixture was set aside. The reaction product was diluted with cold water and filtered. The filtrate was neutralised with sodium carbonate. The precipitate after filtration, washing, and recrystallisation from rectified spirit afforded 5(6)-bromo-2-methylbenzimidazole (9.2 g., 57%), m.p. 210-12°. (Found: N, 12.98. C₈H₇N₂Br requires N, 13.27%.) The m.p. was not altered either on refluxing it with benzene, aniline or treatment with potassium iodide.

(B). *Bromination with 2 Moles of Bromine.*—2-Methylbenzimidazole (10 g., 1M) in acetic acid (75 ml) on bromination with bromine (25.2 g.) in acetic acid (50 ml) and working up as above afforded an orange-coloured product, insoluble in water, and 2-methyl-4, 6 (5, 7)-dibrom benzimidazole (10.2 g., 46.4%), m.p. 212-13°. (Found: N, 9.90. C₈H₆N₂ Br₂ requires N, 9.65%). The orange-coloured precipitate, dissolved in ethanol and neutralised with sodium carbonate, afforded polybromo-2-methylbenzimidazole (5.0 g.), m.p. 234-39°.

(C). *Chlorination.*—A solution of 2-methylbenzimidazole (12.0 g.) in rectified spirit (200 ml) was added to bleaching powder (30 g.) suspension in water (200 ml) over 2hr.

and the mixture was set aside for 2 days. The product was filtered, the residue washed with rectified spirit, and the filtrate and washings were combined and concentrated. The solid left behind was refluxed with benzene for 3 hr. and filtered. The benzene filtrate on concentration afforded 4(7)-chloro-2-methylbenzimidazole (8.8 g., 58.2%) as white plates, m.p. 172°. (Found: N, 17.00. $C_8H_7N_2Cl$ requires N, 16.82%.)

2-Methyl-4(7)-chlorobenzimidazole was recovered (4.0 g., 80%) unchanged when H_2O_2 (10 ml., 30 vol.) was added to a solution of 2-methyl-4(7)-chlorobenzimidazole (5.0 g.) in acetic acid (45 ml) and HCl (conc., 25 ml.) at 0°. It was set aside for 2 days and then diluted and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate.

Benzimidazoles

The benzimidazoles were prepared by Cescon and Day's method²⁴. The mixture of halo-*o*-phenylenediamine, aliphatic acid, and 5.5*N*-HCl was heated under reflux for 6-8 hr., cooled, diluted, and filtered. The filtrate was neutralised carefully at 0° with aqueous ammonia. The benzimidazoles were crystallised from aqueous ethanol.

TABLE III

No.	2-Methylbenzimidazoles.	M.P.	%Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	4-Chloro-	172-73°	54	Colorless plates	$C_8H_7N_2Cl$	16.56	16.82
1	5,7-Dichloro-	200-201°	51	Colorless amorphous powder	$C_8H_6N_2Cl_2$	13.82	14.01
3	5-Bromo-	213-14°	57	Colorless globules	$C_8H_7N_2Br$	12.89	13.27
4	5,7-Dibromo-	214-15°	50	Colorless plates	$C_8H_6N_2Br_2$	9.75	9.65

TABLE IV

No.	<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamines.	M.P.	%Yield.	Properties.	Formula.	%Nitrogen.	
						Found.	Reqd.
1	<i>NN'</i> -Dimethyl-	96-98°	49.5	White needles (fluorescence)	$C_8H_{12}N_2$	20.50	20.50
2	„ -5-chloro-	73-75°	53.3	White needles	$C_8H_{11}N_2Cl$	16.63	16.43
3	„ -5-bromo-,HCl	232-35°	39.5	Brownish powder	$C_8H_{12}N_2ClBr$	10.90	11.13
4	„ -3,5-dibromo-,HCl	267-68°	37.5	Pinkish powder	$C_8H_{11}N_2ClBr_2$	8.50	8.21

Cleavage of Benzimidazoles.—A mixture of 2-methylbenzimidazole (4.65 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) and methyl iodide (35 ml) was heated under reflux for 15 hr. The benzimidazolylmethyl iodide (m.p. 225°, decomp.), thus formed, was filtered, washed with ethanol, mixed with EtOH-KOH (100 ml, 10%), and heated under reflux for 72 hr. The product was diluted with water and extracted with ether; ether extracts were combined, washed and dried over NaOH. The residue after distillation of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure, affording *NN'*-dimethyl-*o*-phenylenediamine (2.3 g., 49.5%), b.p. 150-65/17 mm, m.p.

92-94°, showing dark greenish red fluorescence. The physical properties of other *sym.*-dimethyl-*o*-phenylenediamines are recorded in Table IV. 5-Bromo- and 5,7-dibromo-2-methylbenzimidazoles afforded impure semisolid bromo- *sym.*-*NN'*-dimethyl-*o*-phenylenediamines which were isolated as their hydrochlorides by passing dry hydrogen chloride until saturated in their ethereal solutions.

The attempts to prepare *sym.*-dimethyl-*o*-phenylenediamines from the corresponding amines, using formaldehyde and formic acid, and methylation with methyl iodide of *o*-phenylenediamines resulted in unidentifiable mixtures.

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